

EFFECT OF ADOPTION OF BUDDED CITRUS TECHNOLOGY AMONG FARMERS IN BENUE STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the farm level effect of adoption of budded citrus technology in Benue State. Multistage sampling technique was used. Two out of the three Agricultural Development Programme (ADP) zones in the state were selected. Thirty-two citrus farmers under the state ADP were purposively selected. Data was collected with structured interview schedule. Frequency counts, percentages, ranking, Chi square and PPMC were used for data analysis. Most (65.6%) of the farmers had adopted budded citrus technology between 4 and 20years while 34.4% had adopted the technology more than 20years. They have more than 100.0% returns on investment indicating its profitability in the state. Adoption of budded citrus technology had very high effect on augmentation of income and improved yield among 72.7% and 42.4% of the respondents respectively. Also, 42.4% experienced high poverty reduction as a result of adoption of the technology. Diseases and pests infestation ranked first and second while fire outbreak ranked last as risk factors associated with adoption of the technology. Significant ($p < 0.05$) relationship existed between farm level effect of adoption and sex ($x^2 = 4.09$) and marital status ($x^2 = 10.28$) of the respondents. Concerted effort should be made to improve on adoption of the budded citrus technology by combating the prevailing risk factors with a view to promoting economic gains of citrus farmers in the state.

KEYWORDS: Adoption, technology, budded citrus, farmers

INTRODUCTION

The role of fruits, citrus in particular, cannot be overemphasized in the achievement of nutritional security. Nigeria is presently under utilizing the hectare of land available for fruit production. For instance, the available hectare for citrus production is 1, 300,000 while the estimated hectare under production is 739,000 leaving a balance of 570,000 uncultivated (Bello, 2006).

Citrus is one of the most important fruit tree crops in Nigeria and it is utilized both for fresh consumption and industrial processing (Olaniyan, Amih, Babatola, Umeh, Adebayo, 2000). It surpasses all other fruit trees as raw materials in fruit drink industry and is rated to be among the ten most important fruit tree crops in Nigeria (Adelaja and Olaniyan, 2000; Oyedele, 2000). It is ranked first among the prominence fruits for research in order of national, regional and international importance (NIHORT, 1996; Talabi, 1999; Babatola, 2002; Ogunbaigbe, 2004). The different family of citrus includes grapefruits, tangerines, sweet oranges, tangelos, limes, pumelo, grape, mandarin and lemon (Oyedele, 2005).

Research output in the form of improved technology holds the key to sustained productivity, increased agricultural growth and rural prosperity in Nigeria (Babalola, 2002, Falusi 2010). Success of the agricultural system therefore hinges on provision of solution to constraints of productivity, development of appropriate technologies by National Agricultural Research System (NARS), adequate transfer by the extension sub-system and wide spread adoption by the farmer (Babalola, 2002, Ogunbaigbe, 2004). With the current rate of population growth, increasing levels of consumption and expansion in the global economy, the challenge of producing food and fibre for the global population rests on the technology-driven agricultural system (Robertson and Swinton, 2005; Joshua, 2006). Budded citrus technology is an improvement over the common and well-known seedling tree that could take about seven years before fruiting as against 3-4 years of fruiting for the budded tree.

Citrus is the most important tree crop in Benue State and 85.4% are budded materials indicating high level of adoption budded citrus technology in the State (Benue State Government, 2005). In order to assess the effect of adoption of budded citrus technology in the state and encourage utilization of the unused land area for citrus production among farmers, this study focused on the following specific objectives:

- (i) determine the personal characteristics of the respondents
- (ii) assess the farm level effect of adoption
- (iii) determine the profitability of budded citrus production in established orchard
- (iv) assess the characteristics that enhance adoption
- (v) determine the present risk factors in budded citrus production

Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between the selected personal characteristics of the respondents and the farm level effect of adoption of budded citrus.

METHODOLOGY

Area of study

The study was carried out in Benue State popularly referred to as the “Food Basket of the Nation”. The state is located in the middle belt agro-ecological zone. The total land area is 33,955 kilometers square out of which 23,000 square kilometers are available for arable and tree crop production. About 80% of the population is involved in subsistence farming.

Study population, sampling procedure and sample size

The population for this study is citrus farmers under the coverage of the Benue State Agricultural Development Programme (ADP). The ADP zoning system in the state was used to select the farmers. Multistage sampling technique involving selection of two prominent zones (A and B) for citrus production out of the three in the state, and purposive sampling of citrus homestead farmers was used to identify respondents. A total of 32 farmers were selected and interviewed using pre-tested interview schedule.

Measurement of variables and data analysis

Farmers were asked to indicate their age in years, sex as either “male” or “female”, marital status as “married”, “single” or “widowed”, religion as “Christianity” or “Islam” and educational qualification as “No formal education”, “Primary”, “Secondary” or “Tertiary” to measure their personal characteristics.

Respondents were asked to indicate “Yes, very great effect” = 3, “Yes, great effect” = 2, “Yes, little effect” = 1 or “No effect” = 0 from a list of five items (income augmentation, improved yield, poverty reduction, household food security and unit cost reduction) to measure farm level effect of adoption of the technology. This gave a maximum farm level effect score of 15 and a minimum of 0. This was further categorized as “High” or “Low” using the mean score as cutting point. Mean score and above = High while scores below mean = Low.

Also, from a list of six adoption-enhancing characteristics, they were asked to indicate the level of enhancement of each characteristic as “Greatly enhance” = 2, “Slightly enhance” = 1 or “Do not enhance” = 0. The 12 risk factors associated with adoption were scored as “A risk factor” = 1 or “Not a risk factor” = 0. The factor with highest frequency was ranked highest or most important risk factor while the one with least frequency was ranked last. Profitability of the technology was determined by calculating the difference between the total amount invested and the total income. Data was analyzed using frequency counts, percentages, ranking and PPMC.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Personal characteristic of the farmers

Higher percentage (78.1%) of the respondents were male, with 56.3% and 31.3% within 51-75 and 26-50 years of age respectively, 84.4% married, 40.6% had no formal education, 68.8% were household heads, 50% of the respondent had a household size less than 10 while 36.4% had a household size of 11-20. More than half (58.1%) had adopted budded citrus technology for less than 20 years while 38.7% had been cultivating budded citrus for between 21 and 40 years (Table 1). It has earlier been reported that citrus farming in the North-central zone of Nigeria is male dominated (Alabi *et al*, 2010). Benue State is also the foremost citrus-producing State in the zone and thus it is experiencing male domination. This could also be due to the system of inheritance in the region that accrues land ownership to male children and citrus being a permanent crop can only be planted by the male gender.

Higher percentage of the respondents fall between age 51 and 75 years. This has serious implication for the future as it connotes that the farmers are old and their productivity may be affected. Abandoned orchards were

observed during the survey due to the old age and death of the owners whose children have gone in search of greener pasture and are not interested in farming. The higher literacy level observed contradicted what was obtained by Olajide-Taiwo *et al* (2010) among adopters of LD-88 okra variety in Federal Capital Territory with 61.4 having no formal education. Contrary to common observation of very high illiteracy level among farmers, majority had one form of education which could also be responsible for the wide adoption of the budded citrus technology. This is because the processes involved before adoption is an educational process. In other words, education and training enhances adoption. Researchers have observed significant relationships between adoption of improved technologies and level of training/education of beneficiaries (Ani *et al*, 2004; Ofuoku 2009).

Farm level effect of adoption of budded citrus technology

Adoption of budded citrus variety had very great effects on income augmentation, improved yield and poverty reduction among 75.0%, 43.7% and 40.7% of the respondents respectively. Also, the adoption of the technology had great effect on household food security and nutrition among 46.9% of the farmers among other positive effects (Table 2).

Apart from unit cost reduction which was considered as the variable on which adoption of the technology had either little (40.7%) or great (40.7%) effects, respondents rated the technology as having very great or great effects on the other variables (income augmentation, improved yield, poverty reduction and household food security) considered. With effective marketing channels, improvement in yield will bring about increase in income and consequently poverty reduction among the respondents. This is because there is an improvement in the disposable income of the respondents, thus more is available to be spent on the other basic necessities of life.

Profitability of budded citrus variety among the respondents

In 2009, the estimated cost of production on fully established orchard of 88.6ha (intercropped with other crops) was N879, 350.00 while an income of N17, 427,400.00 was realized. This brings the profit to N16, 548,050.00, which was more than 100.0% return on investment thus implying that budded citrus production is highly profitable.

The estimated profit per hectare is therefore N1, 867,725.73. This was higher than the total profit of N1, 071,000.00 achievable on one ha of budded citrus from the seventh year according to Lawal (2008). An extra profit of N796, 725.73 realized could be due to the fact that many of the citrus orchards considered were more than seven years. Thus, the output and return on investment was more. Also, since the farms have been established for long, farmers' expenses are reduced.

Characteristics that enhance adoption

The three topmost traits which enhanced adoption of budded citrus technology were high yielding, early maturity/fruiting and regular fruiting pattern as opined by 96.9%, 90.6% and 84.4% of the respondents respectively. Other characteristics that greatly enhanced adoption are reduced tree height (59.4%), no thorn (56.3%) and ease of harvesting (56.3%) (Table 3). The three topmost traits enhancing adoption of the budded citrus technology have link with improvement of economic returns to the farmers. One of the major characteristics of a technology which enhances adoption is its economic potentials (Ogunfeditimi, 19981).

With the development of budded citrus technology, scions of the desirable characteristics/traits were budded on the rootstock thereby encouraging the manifestation of the desired traits/character. These are improvement over the seedling trees which are usually low yielding, late fruiting with irregular fruiting pattern, thorny with very tall trees and are not usually true to type. Before the popularization of budded citrus, most citrus orchards in Nigeria comprised seedling trees especially in the southern part of the country (Aiyelaagbe *et al*, 1994)

Risk factors in production of budded citrus

Despite the peculiar characteristics of the budded citrus technology, it is not without risk. The risk factors associated with budded citrus is presented in descending order of importance as: diseases infestation, pests infestation and susceptibility to drought among others. Fire outbreak is the least important risk factor (Table 4)

Diseases and pest infestation problems were widely observed in almost all the citrus producing zones of the country in recent time. It has been reported that the increased production of citrus is limited by the activities of pathogens of both fungal and bacteria origin (NIHORT, 2000). This is an indication that research has to be on

the lookout for measures to combat the outbreak diseases and pests on time. Most of the fruits were observed with dark/black spots while some were hard/thick when touched

The observed low yield of citrus among the respondents could be attributed to pest and diseases infestations which is invariably the expected outcome of their action on the citrus trees. However, risks in terms of farmland slope, death of crops and marketing problems were not so much pronounced among the respondents. Only 21.9% viewed marketing as a risk, this could be as a result of ready market enhanced by short distances between farms and nearness to good road as short as half kilometers in the study area. Buyers come to buy the citrus fruit while on the tree depending on the visual estimation of the number of fruits. This is not so profitable for the farmers but for fear of spoilage and monetary loss, they prefer to sell at the farm gate.

This marketing system according to Benue State Government (2005) forced farmers to use the services of middle men who exploit them. Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (2004) reported that improved domestic marketing and distribution has a great potential for lowering the cost and increasing the range and volume of domestic marketing thereby stimulating increased employment, output and income. Though the respondents did not see marketing as a significant risk, the existing market system does not encourage bargaining power. Accessibility to reliable market information by producers would improve bargaining power, make negotiations more effective and improve farmer's income (Amerose, 2009; Oyedele and Yahaya, 2009). In this type of marketing system bargaining power is lost because farmers may not be informed about the prevailing current market situation. There is need to link up farmers with alternative marketing outlet through appropriate communication and information dissemination.

Correlation Analysis/Relationship between the Respondents Personal Characteristics and Farm Level Effect of Adoption

There was a significant relationship between farm level effect of adoption, sex and marital status (Tables 5 and 6). This implies that adoption having effect on the adopters has to do with the sex of the adopters, this could be as a result of inequality in the number of male and female involved in adoption in the study area. Farmers that are married have the tendency to work harder than unmarried farmers because of the level of responsibilities attached to their marital status.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Budded Citrus technology is well known and adopted among farmers in Benue State. Most of the farmers are literate. Adoption of the technology is profitable in the State. Diseases and pests infestation are the most important risk factors associated with adoption of the technology. Concerted efforts should be made to improve on the existing budded citrus technology by getting varieties that are resistant to prevailing pests and diseases in the different Agro-ecological zones of the Country to encourage wide adoption and improve farmers income. Industrialists, private organization, and processors in particular should be made to appreciate the essence of research and therefore contribute their quota to the development, dissemination and adoption of technology. Effective marketing channels should be introduced to improve on the existing domestic market to avoid exploitation on the part of the farmers

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Table 1: Personal Characteristics of the Respondents

Characteristics	Category	Frequency (%)
Age	≤ 25	4 (12.5)*
	26 – 50	10 (31.3)
	51 – 75	18 (56.2)
Sex	Male	25(75.8)
	Female	7 (24.2)
Marital Status	Single	4 (12.5)
	Married	27 (84.5)
	Widowed	1 (3.0)
Religion	Christianity	31 (96.9)
	Islam	1 (3.1)
Education	No formal education	13 (40.6)
	Primary	11 (34.4)
	Secondary	4 (12.5)
	Tertiary	4 (12.5)
Household size	≤ 10	11 (50.0)
	11 – 20	8 (36.4)
	21 – 30	3 (13.6)
	> 30	1 (3.1)
Head of household	Yes	22 (68.8)
	No	10(31.2)
Years of adoption of budded citrus	≤ 20	21(58.1)
	21 – 40	10(38.7)
	>40	1(3.2)
Number of children	No child	2(6.2)
	1-4	1(3.0)
	5-8	11(33.3)
	9-12	6(18.2)
	13-16	6(18.2)
	>13	6(18.2)
Experience in farming	1-10	3(9.4)
	11-20	2(6.2)
	21-30	9(28.1)
	31-40	15(48.9)
	41-50	3(9.4)

*Figures in parentheses are percentages

Table 2 Farm level effect of budded citrus

Farm level Effect	Very High	High	Low
Income augmentation	24(75.0)	8(25.0)	0(0.0)*
Improved yield	14(43.7)	12(37.5)	6(18.8)
Poverty reduction	13(40.7)	14(43.7)	5(15.6)
Household food security	10(31.3)	15(46.9)	7(21.8)
Unit cost reduction	6(18.6)	13(40.7)	13(40.7)

* Figures in parenthesis are percentages

Table 3: Characteristics that Enhance Adoption

Characteristics	Greatly Enhance	Slightly Enhance	Do not Enhance
Early maturity/fruiting	29(90.6)	3(9.4)	0.0
Regular fruiting pattern	27(84.4)	5(15.6)	0.0
High yielding	31(96.9)	1(3.1)	0.0
Reduced tree height	19(59.4)	12(37.5)	1(3.1)
Lack of thorns	18(56.3)	11(34.4)	3(9.4)
Easy harvesting	18(56.3)	10(31.3)	4(12.4)

Table 4: Ranking of risk factors in citrus production

Risk Factors	Percentage	Rank
Diseases	18(56.3)*	1
Pests	15(46.9)	2
Drought	12(37.5)	3
Low yield	11(34.4)	4
Unstable government policies	8(25.0)	5.5
Marketing	8(25)	5.5
Theft	7(21.9)	7
Farmland slope	5(15.6)	8
Insecure farmland	4(12.5)	9
Fire outbreak	3(9.4)	10

*() Percentages of “Yes” response in parentheses

Table 5: Correlation Analysis/Relationship between the Respondents Personal Characteristics and Farm Level Effect of Adoption

Personal characteristics	R	P	Decision
Age	0.30	0.93	NS
Number of children	0.19	0.30	NS
Household size	0.11	0.54	NS
Years of experience in farming	0.24	0.19	NS
Years of adoption	0.29	0.11	NS

S = Significant, NS = Not Significant

Table 6: Chi Square Analysis showing relationship selected personal characteristics and farm level effect of adoption

Personal characteristics	X ²	Df	P	cc	Decision
Sex	4.09	1	0.04	0.34	S
Marital status	10.28	2	0.01	0.49	S
Religion	0.47	1	0.49	0.12	NS
Education	3.91	3	0.27	0.33	NS
Membership of organization	0.61	2	0.74	0.14	NS

S = Significant, NS = Not Significant

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